

The History of the Kongu Country

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A B S T R A C T

The Kongu Country is one of the earliest territorial divisions of South India included in the ancient home of the Tamils, which extended from Vengadam in the North to Kumari in the South. It figures in classical Tamil Works. It seems to have embraced the whole of the old Coimbatore District, which included Karur and Namakkal taluks, and the southern portion of the Salem District. Talamalai, Velliyangiri, the Palani Hills and Kulittalai, which marked the borders of it, show that it was surrounded by the Chera, Chola and Pandya countries. The famous Ayiraimalai, with a stream issuing from it and a shrine dedicated to the goddess Kadugal, which formed the periodical exodus of the ancient Chera Kings, lay not far from one of its borders, the Palani Hills. The mountain is now called Aivarmalai. The region covering Mala – Nadu, Keralantaka – Valanadu, and Konadu was also on its border. The north eastern portion of Kongu contacted the ancient Pallava Kingdom. The Western Gangas in early times and the Hoysalas in later days occupied portions immediately to the North of the Kongu Country.

Key Words: Kongu, South Indians, Western Gangas.

The History of the Kongu Country

The Kongu Country is one of the oldest territorial divisions of South India. It was bordered on the west and to some extent on the south, by the Chera Country, on the south by the Pandya Country, on the east by the Chola Country and Konadu and on the north by the territory of the Adigaimans. If the last named territory is treated as forming part of Kongu, for which there is no warrant as we find the co- existence of the two from the earliest days, the northern boundary would be the Pallava dominions. Having these territories as boundaries, the central region of Kongu was sheltered by a series of mountain ranges of considerable height such as the Palani hills, the Kollimalai ranges, part of Sherveroys, the Anaimalais and the Nilgiris, and was watered by the Kaveri river with its numerous tributaries – the north ward flowing hallas in the Kollegal Taluk, the Bhavani, the Noyyal and the Amaravati flowing south to north. In spite of these several streams and rivers that were in the country, water scarcity was greatly felt in the region at all times.

In ancient times a highway called Konga- peruvali passed through this country and it seems to have been one of the earliest trade routes of South India which carried on a very busy trade with Rome for the first six centuries. The wealth of the territory lay in its hill produce, silk and beryl, the last of which was produced in large quantities at a place called Padiyur, six and a half miles north west of Kangayam¹¹. Besides these Kongu was noted for gold. Huge hoards of Roman gold coins had been found at several places, such as Kalayamuttar, Karur, Pollachi and Vellalur, a very good breed of bulls and cows from Kangayam is celebrated in the Sangam works^{2 2}.

Kongu, a Territory not a Kingdom

The connotation of the word Kongu may be noted here. This term has a more limited application than the similar ones Chera, Chola, Pandya, Pallava etc. While each of the latter conveys to our mind not only a particular country, but also a kula or race, its people and its king, the former, Kongu means exclusively a country; it does not denote any kula or race or king till a very late date. We hear of ‘Sola – kula’. ‘Pandya – vamsa’, ‘Pallava- anvaya’, etc., but not of ‘Kongu – kula’. It may be noted, however, that the words Kongar and Kongar – Ko are applied to the people and the king of Kongu, who held it for the time being, but that none

¹ Sewell's list Vol. I, p. 220.

² Padirrupattu vv. 22 and 77.

of the later kings of the Kongu country called himself a Kongu- deva or Kongu- deva Maharaja, or of being of Kongu- kula- raja. This state of things extended till the eight century A.D.³³.

The difference in the connotation of the word Kongu from other similar ones pointed out above seems strongly to indicate that the country did not belong to, and was not ruled by, any particular dynasty of its own. It will be noted in the sequel that a number of kings held sway over the Kongu country in later times and that none of them had any distinguishing epithet, surname or title, such as Maran, Sadiyan, Valudi and Pandya deva of the Pandyas, Valavan, Sembayan, Rajakesari, Parakesari and Solamaharaja of the Cholas; or Villavan, Seramanar and Kerala of the Cheras. Instead, we often find the rulers of Kongu (from the earliest times to the latest) calling themselves by Chera, Chola, Pandya names, and adopting their surnames, epithets and titles, sometimes indiscriminately. Some chiefs of the 13th century even declared themselves to be the lineal descendants of very early Chera kings who were the first rulers of the northern part of Kongu. We have yet to discover if even those kings that were invested with the hereditary rule of the province of Kongu had at any time any distinct and distinguishing emblem of royalty.

Wealth of Kongu

Hill products of various kinds from the Kolli, Anaimalai, Nilgiris, Sherveros and other ranges of hills enriched the country in olden days. It was also noted for a special kind of gold and a gem of sea- green colour which were highly prized by the nations of the ancient civilised world. The people of Kongu were remarkable for their active engagement in agriculture and other industries. The country was noted from the earliest times for a fine breed of cows and bulls which served the people well in many ways. The skill and energy with which the people of Kongu sunk very deep wells and brought out water by breaking hard rocks with their pickaxes draw the admiration of the ancient bards who celebrated them in their songs. These wells supplemented to a great extent the limited water supply of the few small rivers of the country and enabled the people to convert arid tracts into arable lands.

Speaking of Idangali – Nayanar, one of the canonised Saiva Saints, the ‘Periyarpuram’ states that he came in the line of Adittan, one of Kongu the summit of the Ponnambalam temple.

³ See page 99 para 2 of Ep. Ind. Vol. XXX No. 19.

An Indiscreet Identification

Prof. K. A. Nilakanta Sastri and Mr. T.N. Subramanian, have conjointly contributed an article to the Epigraphia Indica on the Tingalur inscription of Konattan Vikrama Chola wherein they have done me the honour of referring to my Historical Sketches of Acient Dekhan in a note. To which I draw public attention owing to its importance so that the same may not be repeated by others. While referring to Aditya's covering the pinnacle of the Siva Temple with gold mentioned in the Periyapuram, they say "Mr. K. V. S. Aiyer takes this as referring to a certain Aditya of the Kodumbalur family who gilded the dancing hall of a Nataraja temple in Kongu, which may be at Perur, or Kodumudi or any other place in Kongu. This interpretation does not follow the tradition recorded. Further Sirkambalam can only mean Chidambaram and no other place". All authorities such as Numbi Andar Nambi, Sekkilar, the author of the Periyapuram, merely state that Indagaliyar was a king ruling with his capital at the city of Kodumbalur in Konadu and was the earliest ancestor of the Aditya who covered the pinnacle of some Siva temple in Kongu with gold or with gold obtained from Kongu. The rulers of Konadu are styled Irukkuvels. That they were Yadavas is distinctly stated in the Muvarkoyil inscription which is much later than the time of Langaliyar.

The authors have correctly pointed out that I have not identified Adittan the lincal descendant of Idangaliyar of Yadava race with the Chola Aditya of the Solar race, whose son Parantaka is said in the Leiden plates and Tiruvalangadu grant to have gilded the Chirrambalam. There can be no identity between the Yadava Aditya and Solar Chola Aditya as has been assumed by Prof. K. A. Nilakanta Sastri and Mr. T. N. Subramanian. I hereby assure my friends that I shall never commit such a kind of incorrigible mistake which the Saivites will call an impious and profane offence. This note is a warning to others not to commit the same mistake misguided by the general names Aditya, Chirrambalam or Ponambalam. Any large Siva temple in South India such as those at Madurai, Tiruvalangadu etc. will surely have a dancing hall small or big. Chirrambalam or perambalam.

Finally, I may add that the very king whose inscription they had edited, as if by way of denouncing any such attempt of equating the Konattan with the Chola, loudly proclaims that he was a "Konattan" though bearing the name of the Chola.

Divisions Of The Kongu Country

Though generally two divisions of Kongu are recognised viz, the Northern and Southern, there are epigraphical and literary evidences to show that there was at least one other division on the western side. The last is mentioned both in a hymn of the ‘Saiva Saint Sundaramarti Nayanar and in the Madras Museum Plates of Jatilavarman⁴⁴. Tradition marks the small river Karaipottanaru as the boundary of Kongu, Chola and Pandya territories. This stream runs south wards through the Nmakkal Taluk and falls into the Kaveri at a point 11 miles East of Karur. A large embankment carries the boundary from the river southwards⁵⁵. In this tract lay Mala-nadu which supplied the Malava army to the Kongu kings⁶⁶. Northern Kongu was probably the country to the north of the river Kaveri while the southern Kongu must have comprised almost the whole of the Coimbatore District. The four main divisions or Districts had in them several sub- divisions. Inscription reveal the names of more than 30 of them. Kondadu, bordered on Kongu, was separated from it by an embankment running in continuation of the river Karaipotaru, wand comprised most part of the former Pudukkottai State. One of the inscription of Konapuram is the Dharapuram taluk mentions Paratakapuram alias Rajarajapuram⁷⁷ and another of the time of Krishnadevamaharaja calls Rajarajapuram as the capital of Kongu- mandalam⁸⁸. The place is evidently Dharapuram.

The Kollimalai hill, with the country surrounding it, is celebrated in ancient Tamil literature as being originally subject to the sway of a chieftain named Ori⁹⁹. He was renowned not only as a powerful archer but also as one of the most generous persons¹⁰¹⁰. It is said that the Malaiyaman king of Mullar named Kari killed this chief and bestowed his country on the Chera¹¹¹¹. The possession of the Kolli hill by the Chera enabled him to assume the title. ‘Kollipporuna Another Chera king is styled ‘Kolliyoraduporuna¹²¹². From the Padigam at the end of the 8th Ten ‘Padirrupattu’, it is learnt that the Kongu chieftain who was defeated by the Chera Peruncheral Irumporai, was in possession the hill embraced a number of villages. The hill had a high peak, and the sides had splendid forests of fruit- bearing trees. The region

⁴ See the hymn commencing with the word madittadu and Ind. Ant. Vol. XXII. P. 73.

⁵ Sewels list of Antiquities, Vol. I. pp, 203, 262

⁶ Adigaiman Neduman Anji is described as “the head of the Malavas”.

⁷ No. 139 of AR. For 1920.

⁸ Ibid No. 213.

⁹ Kolliy – anda – val-vil-Ori (p. 158):

¹⁰ Ombav – igai – viral veyyon (P.152) and val- vil- Ori. (Agam 206).

¹¹ Agam 200: Mullur- Mannan Kaja – rodi – k Kari sells nallisai nirutta val – vil – Ori – kkoliru Seralarkitta sevverpalavin – payankeju Kolli.

¹² Padirrupattu 77 and 81.

received copious rains¹³¹³. In later times the Kollimalai hill and the surrounding fertile south which in early times had passed from the hill chieftain Ori to the Chera was included in the Kongu territory.

Temples of Kongu

Of the temples of Kongu, even have been celebrated in the hymns of the Devaram. These are Avinasi, Tirumurganpandi. Bhavini, Thiruchehengdu, Kodumudi, Karuvur and Venjainangadalur. Saint Gnanasambhanda has contributed hymns on Bhavani¹⁴¹⁴, Tiruchehengodu¹⁵¹⁵ Pandikkodumudi¹⁶¹⁶ and Karuvar¹⁷¹⁷. Sundaramirtinayanar has sung on Tiruppukkoliyar Avinasi¹⁸¹⁸. Tirumurganpandi¹⁹¹⁹, Venjaman – gudalur²⁰²⁰ and Kodumudi²¹²¹, while Tirunavukkarasu Nayanar has sung on Kodumudi²²²², alone. In these hymns Tirumurganpandi is spoken of as a great city and Venjamangaudalar, which was picturesquely situated on the east bank of the river Serraru, also appears to have been a city of importance; it had high walls, palatial buildings, towers and pavilions touching the very skies²³²³ surrounded by groves of all kinds of fruit bearing trees.

Besides these, two other temples of this province are referred to in the sacred hymns of the Saiva Nayanmars. These are the famous Siva temples at Perar and Kolli. In Adaivu – tiruthandagam included in the 7th Tirumaurai the temple at Kolli is described as Kattar- kamal kolli- Araippalli in the Kshetrakkovai included in the same Tirumurai. Sundaramurti- Nayanar in his hymn ‘madittadu’ refers to Perur as ‘mi- Kongil – ani – Kanchivay – p Perur. The temples referred to above, having been mentioned or celebrated in hymns of the early

¹³ Surumbar- solai- ppeyar- Kolli (p.81) Karai vilnderutaru- majai- seral- nedun – kottu- Kollipporuna.

¹⁴ The hymn commences with “pandar – viran”.

do. With “kodugu- ven – jilai”.

¹⁵ Commences with “venda – venniru”.

¹⁶ do. With “pennamar- meniyinan”.

¹⁷ do. With “tondela- malar- tuviye”.

¹⁸ do. With “Erran marakken”.

¹⁹ do. With “kodugu- ven – jilai”.

²⁰ do. With “Erikkun Kadir”.

²¹ do. With “marru- pparrena”

²² do. With “sittanai sivanai”.

²³ Serrar- ata!) kil – karai- mel Valangon- madil- maligai- gopuramum- animandapamum- ivai anjuntannul vilanga- madi-toy- Venjamakkudal.

Saiva Saints must have attained notoriety before the seventh century A.D. But it must be said that the structural monuments which enshrine the gods in these places are not the original ones but are later and belong to the time of the Kongu- Konattar kings though not of a very early date. The sculptures in the Perur temple show exquisite workmanship and reflect greatly on the skill of the workmen.

The earliest monuments of the Kongu country are the rock cut caves with beds, with or without inscriptions, dating so far back as the third century B.C. They have been discovered in the Arunattar hill at Pugalur near Karur, and in the hill near Arasalur near Erode. The inscription on the beds contain the names most probably of the Bauddha Bikshus whose order prevented them from remaining in villages and towns after the night fall. They are written in the Brahmi script and Tamil language. Other earliest monuments of the Kongu country are the rock- cut shrines of Narasimha and Ranganatha found at Namakkal and the date of their execution cannot be far distant from those which came into existence in the early Pallava period and are found in the Chingleput District. The sculptors that worked in the Namakkal Cave temples must have derived their inspiration from or emigrated from the neighbouring Pallava territory.

Rock- Cut Cave Temples at Namakkal

Of the two rock- cut Vishnu temples, one of the god Sri Narashimha and the other of Sri Ranganatha, the latter is called in its inscription ‘Atiyendra Vishnugriha’ and the king bears the Prakritipriya, Naravahsna, Utpalakarnika and Udarachitta, all speaking of his high kingly qualities²⁴. In a later inscription, this temple is called Pallikonda Perumal while the other temple is named Singapperumal²⁵.

The Arappalisvara temple, situated in the village of Valappanadu in the Namakkal Taluk, had been held very sacred by people. The division of Kollimalai to which it belonged was included in virasolamandalam, the name by which the province of Kongu was called after its conquest by the kings of the Vijayalaya line.

²⁴ No. 7 of 1906.

²⁵ No. 10 of 1906. Two inscriptions of Tribh. Konerinmaikondan Sundara Pandya (13/06) and of Tribh Konerinmaikondan (14/06) register gifts of the village of Vanavanmadevi in Elurnadu, a district of Vada Kongu to a doctor and refers to the three assemblies of ‘sabha, nadu and nagarattar’.

Conclusion

Vira- chola, it may be noted, was one of the surnames of Pranataka I, the successor of Aditya I to whom conquest of Kongu has to be attributed. Aditya conquered Kongu and Parantaka I stabilised it by adding it to the Chola province. Not long after the reign of Parantaka I, one of his pious daughters- in- law, Parantakan Madevadigalar alias Sembiyanmadeviyar, the mother of Uttama Chola, made a rich endowment to this temple of Arappalisvarattu- Alvar and made the members of the assemblies of certain villages in Kollimalainadu meet from the interest the expenses of festivals to be conducted during Sankaramnas (vishus).

Reference

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- ¹ Sewell's list Vol. I, p. 220.
- ² Padirrupattu vv. 22 and 77.
- ³ See page 99 para 2 of Ep. Ind. Vol. XXX No. 19.
- ⁴ See the hymn commencing with the word madittadu and Ind. Ant. Vol. XXII. P. 73.
- ⁵ Sewels list of Antiquities, Vol. I. pp, 203, 262.
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- ¹³ Surumbar- solai- ppeyar- Kolli (p.81) Karai vilmdertaru- majai- seral- nedun – kottu- Kollipporuna.
- ¹⁴ The hymn commences with "pandar – viran".
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